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MEASURING GEOMETRIC THINKING OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS WITH VAN HIELE TEST

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ABSTRACT

The van Hiele couple have developed a method of identifying different cognitive levels for geometric thinking. According to their theory, the goal of teaching is to reach these levels step-by-step. This is measured by the Usiskin test, which was created in the 1980s. It has been used all around the world, except at technical universities in Hungary. The test's results show whether a necessary level of logical thinking and reasoning for higher education has been reached and serve as a guide to forming groups in education for topic processing. People who are on different levels differ in their geometric thinking, which results in a person with a higher score, who won't accept the arguments of a person with a lower level of geometric thinking.

We completed the test with 130 freshmen with the following results: 68 of them were ranked at level five, 13 at level four, 39 at level three, 1 person reached level two, 7 people level one and 2 of them only reached level zero with permissive evaluation and a full roster. 62.3% were at least on the level of formal conclusions indicating a general level of mathematical thinking. These students tend to substantiate their statements, and are often able to prove them correctly. In our research, we analyzed the

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participants' test results and examined their scores in Calculus, having in mind how their results connect to their level of geometric thinking.

The importance of the van Hiele test is that it 'measures' logical reasoning.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the mathematical education of engineering students the non-Euclidean geometry is a neglected field. The structure of the calculus subjects is often based on examples that are closely applicable to real-life problems, thus resulting in proofs being relegated to the background in many cases compared to the mathematical education of scientific programs. Nevertheless, the volume of the curriculum and the pace of the semester cause difficulties for many engineering students after secondary school studies. Students coming to BME for mechatronics engineering and energy engineering programs are high-skilled students who have been admitted to the university with a high enrollment points and have been introduced to several details of the first semester calculus course in their secondary school studies. In case of these students, there is an opportunity to alleviate the constraints mentioned earlier and to introduce a curriculum requiring a higher level of abstraction.

1.1 Motivation and goals

This commitment is necessarily more difficult and requires more energy from an educational point of view. In order to successfully complete the educational goal along this path, it is necessary to classify the geometric thinking of the students into levels, as a prerequisite for achieving the goal is that the students are at an appropriate level in this regard.

Such a test, which assesses students, is also useful in the traditional method of teaching, as we can get a more complete picture of the students' thought process. In the present case, such a test helps us to get started, as it shows which methods of reasoning are expedient and which logical steps will most likely cause a problem in comprehension. In addition, in the case of a differentiated teaching method, it is worth treating students with the same level of thinking in homogeneous groups in order to increase the efficiency of communication between them. The Van Hiele theory and tests based on it are suitable for assessing students' levels of thinking.

Teacher-student communication plays a key role in successful education. It is not possible to reach a higher level of understanding if students are approached inappropriately. During the educational process, students should be educated from their individual level of understanding and the goal is to bring them to a higher level of understanding. If students' level of understanding is not assessed or teachers do not develop communication accordingly, the teaching process will fail in terms of developing the thinking process and problem-solving ability. In this case, no more than a transfer of factual material can take place. In contrast, if the level of comprehension has been properly assessed, there is room for improvement in small steps with proper communication.

1.2 The van Hiele test

Pierre van Hiele and Dina van Hiele-Geldorf developed a theory in 1957 suitable for understanding the process of geometric thinking. In their work, they developed five levels of understanding from the level of recognition to the level of formal logic. The different levels mean having the following ability:

Level 1: Candidates are able to recognize shapes. They are able to perceive the shapes based on their appearance, but they are not able to observe their details and properties. Without it, they are not yet able to understand the connections. For example, they recognize that the shape is square, but that it is a rectangle they are unable to determine.

Level 2: Candidates are able to identify shapes with their properties. For example, they know that a quadrangle whose angles are 90 degrees is a rectangle. They do not yet have the knowledge to understand the relation between a set of rectangles and squares.

Level 3: Candidates identify shapes by their definition. For example, they will be able to recognize that a square is also a rectangle. In addition, they understand simple proofs, are able to argue and take proof steps.

Level 4: Candidates are familiar with the meaning of the axiom system. They understand the difference between axioms and statements/definitions, but are not necessarily able to break down their proof into axioms. They can deduce evidence, but they don't feel they need to prove "seemingly obvious" claims. For example, if a third line is perpendicular to a line perpendicular to a line, then the parallelism of the first and third lines is felt to be obvious without proof.

Level 5: Candidates are able to think abstractly. They are able to work with other axiom systems, so they are able to use non-Euclidean geometry, such as Bolyai's hyperbolic geometry. This level is the highest in the Van Hiele system, usually only achievable by individuals with exceptional talent (in secondary school: mostly students taking special mathematics faculty, in higher education: mathematics, engineering students).

1.3 Place of geometry in Hungarian Math education

The most common test designed to measure the levels mentioned above was born in the 1980s. [1] Due to the structure of the Hungarian public education, it can be used very well to measure Hungarian students, so we used this as well. The goals formulated in the national core curriculum of public education in Hungary are discussed in detail in the framework curriculum. In Hungary, education is centralized - the national core curriculum defines it more loosely, while the framework curriculum defines the content of education more strictly. As a result, it can be expected that the map of geometric understanding in Hungary should be uniform.

Szabó and his colleagues examined the level of geometric understanding associated with the knowledge acquired in public education at a given age. [2] In their work, they found that each van Hiele level can be assigned to primary school and secondary

school classes, respectively. The curriculum defined for the lower grades of primary school includes the recognition of triangles, squares, and rectangles, and their production by drawing freely or specifying properties. This can be assigned to level 1. For grades 5 and 6, students should be familiar with the illustrative concept of planes figures and polygons (triangles, squares). So for these classes, students have to reach level 2. They should then be able to group different shapes according to their properties, so they are expected to reach level 3 by the end of sixth grade. Later, at the end of grades 7 and 8, students should approach level 4 by being able to make statements based on their observations and they should have a need for proofs. Overall, students should reach the 3rd Van Hiele level during the 8 years of primary school and the 4th level by the end of secondary school according to the requirements of the national core curriculum.

The aim of our measurement was to examine the proportion of our students at the 4th level. If they sufficiently meet this prerequisite, the teaching of the calculus subject can be developed accordingly, since in this case we have the opportunity to teach our students knowledge that requires a higher level of abstraction. When explaining new material or proving statements, we can communicate in a way that suits their levels of thinking.

Given the content of the national core curriculum, it would be a legitimate expectation that there is nothing to prevent us from assuming the existence of level 4 even in engineering education. Thus, it becomes possible to understand and perform formal logical operations and conclusions regardless of the specific geometric interpretation. It should not be a problem to recognize the general laws of logic and to understand the connections between different axiom systems.

However, it is worrying that studies conducted in teacher education in Hungary have shown that there is a large gap between the theoretical expectations and the actual expectations. [2], [3] As a result, many students complete their secondary school studies with a lower level of understanding than level 4. Knowing these, we considered it necessary to carry out an assessment test that examines the thinking levels of students studying in elite programs in Hungarian technical higher education.

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 Structure of the test

The test created by Usisikin consists of 25 questions and measures 5 competing competencies. Each competency is designed to be measured by 5 questions. The questions are a test tasks and exactly one of the five possible answers is correct. They have 35 minutes to complete the tasks, regardless of age or previous education. Based on the test results, participants will either be classified into one of the Van Hiele levels or will be declared non-classifiable. The level of classified participants can be 0,1,2,3,4 or 5. During the classification 0 means the complete lack of competencies and 5 means the existence of the highest level of competence.

The abbreviated description is based on [1] and full definitions of the levels can be found here. According to Van Hiele theory, one can only possess a competency belonging to one level if one also possesses all the competencies preceding the level. For example, if someone met the criteria for Levels 1, 2, 3, and 4 during the test, their Van Hiele level is 4. However, if someone met the criteria for levels 1, 2, and 4, but not for level 3, they cannot be classified for any of the levels because they should have met level three for level four as well. (However, it can be said about the person that the Van Hiele level reaches two) From now on, such non-classifiable participants will be referred to as “not fit”. There are two methods for evaluating tests. According to the first method, the participants have a competence belonging to one level if at least three of the five tasks related to the given competence are solved correctly. (hereafter inclusive Van Hiele level). For the other method, this number is 4 (hereafter exclusive Van Hiele level).

2.2 Investigated group

The test was completed by 130 first-year students who are first-year mechatronics and energy engineering students.

2.3 Background of the investigated group

The students who form the basis of our study were admitted to the two programs with the highest admission score in Hungary's leading technical institution. In the case of mechatronics engineering students, 59 people (64.1%) took their final exam at advanced level, while in the case of energy engineering students, 41 people (66.1%). The participating students all studied mathematics at an advanced level, which means they had at least 5 mathematics lessons a week in secondary school and their secondary school curriculum included differential and integral calculus.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Distribution of answers

The percentage distribution of answers to the test questions and the average time spent on the questions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The percentage distribution of the answers and the average time spent on each questions

No	Answ. A	Answ. B	Answ. C	Answ. D	Answ. E	No Answ.	Average time
1	0,00%	93,85%	0,77%	3,85%	0,77%	0,77%	0:00:14
2	0,00%	0,00%	0,77%	98,46%	0,00%	0,77%	0:00:15
3	0,00%	0,00%	96,92%	0,00%	2,31%	0,77%	0:00:13
4	0,00%	96,15%	0,00%	1,54%	1,54%	0,77%	0:00:14
5	0,77%	0,00%	6,15%	0,00%	92,31%	0,77%	0:00:21
6	1,54%	91,54%	3,08%	3,08%	0,00%	0,77%	0:00:50
7	5,38%	1,54%	1,54%	3,08%	84,62%	3,85%	0:00:59

8	80,00%	0,77%	2,31%	3,85%	12,31%	0,77%	0:00:47
9	0,00%	0,00%	97,69%	0,00%	1,54%	0,77%	0:00:31
10	5,38%	3,85%	6,15%	72,31%	11,54%	0,77%	0:01:31
11	0,00%	0,77%	96,92%	0,77%	0,77%	0,77%	0:00:35
12	0,00%	96,92%	1,54%	0,00%	0,77%	0,77%	0:01:02
13	96,15%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	3,08%	0,77%	0:00:14
14	86,92%	3,08%	0,00%	0,00%	9,23%	0,77%	0:00:40
15	3,85%	86,92%	0,77%	1,54%	6,15%	0,77%	0:00:56
16	7,69%	6,15%	52,31%	28,46%	4,62%	0,77%	0:02:10
17	6,92%	6,15%	80,00%	3,08%	3,08%	0,77%	0:01:12
18	7,69%	5,38%	1,54%	82,31%	2,31%	0,77%	0:01:16
19	17,69%	15,38%	21,54%	42,31%	1,54%	1,54%	0:00:55
20	41,54%	2,31%	7,69%	38,46%	9,23%	0,77%	0:02:05
21	3,85%	90,77%	1,54%	0,00%	3,08%	0,77%	0:01:32
22	14,62%	3,08%	5,38%	11,54%	64,62%	0,77%	0:01:23
23	19,23%	1,54%	3,08%	70,00%	5,38%	0,77%	0:01:05
24	3,08%	13,85%	7,69%	68,46%	6,15%	0,77%	0:01:04
25	0,00%	35,38%	0,77%	55,38%	6,92%	1,54%	0:01:38

The following bar chart shows the proportion of correct answers and the proportion of the most common incorrect answers.

Fig. 2. The proportion of correct and most common wrong answers

3.2 Possible explanation for most common wrong answers

Some explanation for typical wrong answers: Question 1: Which is a square? The fact that answer D was marked as correct in some cases may be the result of a misreading. The first syllable of the words square and quadrangle is the same in Hungarian. Question 4: Which is a square? Here, the choice of answer 'E' can be explained by the misreading mentioned earlier. Question 5: Which is a parallelogram? If only a few students, but a few made the mistake of not considering the rhombus as a parallelogram. In the case of question 7, the false answer should have been marked, but some must have inadvertently marked the first true statement. In the case of question 8, the only incorrect answer should have been indicated. Several students marked the answer 'E' that all statements were true. The only erroneous statement regarding the length of the diagonals was not noticed. For question 10, one had to choose from the statements about the deltoid determined by the intersections and centers of the circles, which statement was not always true. Although answer 'E' is not always true, the task was to choose between answers A, B, C, and D. In answering question 13, there were students who did not consider the square to be a rectangle. Question 14 seeks to answer the question of whether students correctly interpret the concept of a subset. Those who marked the answer 'E' as correct do not understand "All squares are rectangles, but not all rectangles are squares." types of statements. The statement in question 16 is true for any arbitrary triangle, it is likely that many were confused by this and therefore the answer 'D' was marked. However, based on the text of the problem, it can only be said that the statement is true for any right triangle. In Problems 17 and 18, a common mistake was made by several people who did not understand what the condition was, what the statement was, and what it meant to reverse a conditional statement. The aim of Problem 19 is to ask about the essential properties of the axiomatic structure. The task is really not easy and the many incorrect answers show that the students did not understand the essence of the axiomatic system. This is perhaps not so surprising, as this kind of rigorous structure is not strongly part of secondary school math education. Solving Problem 20 is easy for students who are familiar with non-Euclidean geometries, but difficult for others. Non-Euclidean geometries are not discussed in Hungarian public education. In Task 22, perhaps inadvertence is the reason why a few students marked the answer 'A'. They did not pay attention to the fact that the sentence is about halving the angle. Constructing half angles is a primary school curriculum and it doesn't usually cause problems for students. Question 23 is easily answered by those who have heard of hyperbolic geometry. This is not part of the curriculum in Hungarian secondary schools, although its existence is often mentioned. The Hungarian János Bolyai - whose first name is referred by J in the task - had important results in discovering this geometry. Question 24 also assumes a much more general approach to mathematics than that acquired by the majority of secondary school students. In question 25, the most common incorrect answer 'B' illustrates a typical error: we know that p implies q , from which several incorrectly concluded that p negates implies q negates.

3.3 Van Hiele levels

The table below shows the inclusive and exclusive Van Hiele levels of the students we examined.

Table 2. The inclusive and exclusive Van Hiele levels of the investigated group

inclusive Van Hiele			exclusive Van Hiele		
Van Hiele level	Number of students	Cumulative sum	Van Hiele level	Number of students	Cumulative sum
5	67	67	5	27	27
4	15	82	4	12	39
3	6	88	3	26	65
2	0	88	2	1	66
1	0	88	1	2	68
0	0	88	0	3	71
not fit	42	-	not fit	59	-

For students participating in the study, the average of the inclusive van Hiele levels was 4.693 and the standard deviation was 0.594. While the average of the exclusive van Hiele levels is 3.732. In this case, the standard deviation is 1.298. If we do not use the 'not fit' category, the inclusive and exclusive van Hiele levels are as follows.

Table 2. The inclusive and exclusive Van Hiele levels of the investigated group without "no answers"

inclusive Van Hiele			exclusive Van Hiele		
Van Hiele level	Number of students	Cumulative sum	Van Hiele level	Number of students	Cumulative sum
5	67	67	5	27	27
4	15	82	4	12	39
3	40	122	3	65	104
2	1	123	2	1	105
1	5	128	1	21	126
0	2	130	0	4	130

If all students who completed the test are graded, then the average of the inclusive van Hiele levels is 4.015 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.207 and the average of the exclusive van Hiele levels is 3.085 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.364.

It can be stated that using the 'not fit' category, the proportion of students who did not reach the level required by the Hungarian intermediate level graduation, calculated

with the exclusive van Hiele levels, is below 5%. This is not necessarily due to student deficiencies. It is also possible that because this test had no stakes or consequences, some were frivolous in completing the test. In terms of inclusive van Hiele levels, all students reached at least the third level. If the 'not fit' category is not used, this ratio is close to 8% for inclusive van Hiele levels, while it is as high as 18% for exclusive van Hiele levels. Using inclusive van Hiele levels, 64% of students have at least the fourth van Hiele level. Using the exclusive van Hiele levels, the same rate is 32%.

4 DISCUSSION

In Hungarian secondary schools, education is organized around the preparation for the matura exam to be completed at the end of the studies. Szabó and his colleagues examined whether the matura exam's expectations were in line with the objectives set out in the national core curriculum. [2] It was found that the intermediate level matura exam requires no more than level 3. Thus, if the emphasis in the examinations is not on problem-solving ability but on performing routine tasks, it is not surprising that this will also play a greater role in education. Advanced matura exam tasks presuppose the existence of a higher level of geometric thinking.

5 CONCLUSION

With a minor exception in the Hungarian higher education system, the matura exam also plays the role of the university entrance examination. For this reason, there is a strong emphasis on preparing for the matura exam in secondary school. As a result, it is not surprising that students' level of thinking develops in line with the exam requirements. As the study was based on students studying in elite programs, the results are better than the domestic and international results published so far. These circumstances allow us to expand the traditional calculus curriculum and conduct the education of mechatronics and energy engineering students at a higher level of abstraction.

REFERENCES

- [1] Usiskin, Z. (1982) Van Hiele levels and achievement in secondary school geometry, Final Report of the Cognitive Development and Achievement in Secondary School Geometry Project Department of Education, *University of Chicago, US*.
- [2] Szabó, Cs., Bereczky-Zámbó, Cs., Muzsnay, A. Szeibert, J. (2020), Students' non-development in high school geometry, *Annales Mathematicae et Informaticae*, pp. 309-319.
- [3] Kónya, E. (2003), A tanítójelöltek geometriai gondolkodásának jellegzetességei, *Iskolakultúra*, pp. 51-61.